

LLMs in Security Testing and Monitoring: An Initial Study

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Abstract. Cyber threats are becoming increasingly complex, causing traditional security systems to struggle in keeping up and highlighting the need for advanced solutions. Large Language Models (LLMs), such as OpenAI’s ChatGPT and Meta AI’s LLaMA, have shown great potential to transform cybersecurity workflows with their abilities in natural language understanding, pattern recognition, and automated reasoning. These models are particularly promising for tasks like network monitoring, threat detection, and security alert triage. However, challenges related to the reliability of outputs, adversarial risks, and ethical concerns must be addressed. This paper presents a comprehensive survey of LLM-based approaches for security testing and evaluates three open-access LLMs, including Mistral-7B, Qwen3-8B, and Llama3.1-8B, demonstrating their ability to enhance security alert analysis. Our findings suggest that LLMs can improve alert clarity and usability, making them more accessible to non-experts while providing valuable insights for developers.

Keywords: Large Language Model, Cybersecurity, Advanced Threats, Cyberdefense, Testing and Monitoring

1 Introduction

As cyber threats grow increasingly complex and frequent, the demand for intelligent, adaptable, and user-friendly security testing tools has become more pressing. Traditional rule-based systems and signature-based detection mechanisms often struggle to keep up with rapidly evolving attack vectors. Recently, Large Language Models (LLMs) have emerged as powerful tools that can transform cybersecurity workflows. Their capabilities in natural language understanding, pattern recognition, and automated reasoning offer exciting possibilities for enhancing security processes [17]. Several LLMs, such as OpenAI’s ChatGPT and Meta AI’s LLaMA, have gained widespread popularity due to their ability to analyze, summarize, and generate human-readable content from complex technical data. This makes them particularly promising for network monitoring, threat detection, and alert triage, which are critical components of modern security testing pipelines.

The intersection of LLMs and cybersecurity has sparked renewed interest within the cybersecurity community [25,8]. Several tools now leverage LLMs to

enhance security testing and monitoring. For example, OpenAI’s GPT-3 and ChatGPT are used to assist in threat intelligence and vulnerability assessments by analyzing cybersecurity reports and identifying patterns. For instance, IBM’s Watson for Cyber Security automates the analysis of unstructured data to generate actionable insights, and SIEM systems like Splunk use LLMs for log analysis and threat detection. Recently, ChatAFL [18] leverages pre-trained LLMs to perform grammar-aware mutations and predict the next input when fuzzing protocols to produce more effective inputs. These tools showcase the potential of LLMs to improve cybersecurity operations in different areas.

Challenges. Integrating LLMs into security testing and monitoring workflows presents several challenges. One key issue is ensuring the reliability and trustworthiness of LLM-generated outputs. Biases in training data can lead to inaccurate conclusions, potentially resulting in false positives or false negatives in security assessments. The interpretability of LLM-generated insights is another significant concern. Understanding the rationale behind their decisions is crucial for effective security responses, but the "black-box" nature of these models can limit their usefulness in real-world applications.

Additionally, the complexity of security alerts generated by monitoring systems such as Suricata [4] and Zeek [5] poses another challenge. While these alerts are rich in technical detail, they can be difficult for non-experts to understand, reducing their effectiveness in environments lacking experienced security analysts. To improve clarity and actionability, LLMs could enhance alert interpretation and usability, but this requires a deep understanding of their capabilities, limitations, and their integration into security workflows. Furthermore, concerns about adversarial manipulation, reliability, and ethical implications must be addressed to ensure the secure, reliable, and responsible use of LLMs in cybersecurity.

Proposal. In this paper, we provide a comprehensive exploration of the applications of LLMs in cybersecurity, with a specific focus on security testing and monitoring. We aim to address existing challenges by first presenting a thorough survey of LLM-based approaches in cybersecurity testing, particularly emphasizing network monitoring and threat detection. We examine how recent advances in LLMs have been utilized to automate security tasks and explore their potential to improve the quality and usability of security alerts. Building on this foundation, we propose a concrete use case to demonstrate the application of LLMs in security alert analysis. Through a comparative evaluation of three state-of-the-art open-access models, including Mistral-7B, Qwen3-8B, and Llama3.1-8B, we showcase their effectiveness in assessing and explaining security alerts across key evaluation criteria, including accuracy, clarity, completeness, actionability, and false positive assessment. Our findings aim to offer valuable guidance for both users and developers of security monitoring tools. For users, LLM-generated analyses can enhance understanding and response to alerts, making security tools more accessible to non-experts. For developers, in-

sights derived from LLM evaluations can inform improvements in alert quality, user experience, and overall system performance.

Contributions. Our contributions are as follows.

- We present a comprehensive survey of LLM-based approaches in cybersecurity testing, with a focus on network monitoring and threat detection.
- We conduct a comparative evaluation of three state-of-the-art open-access LLMs Mistral-7B, Qwen3-8B, and Llama3.1-8B, demonstrating their effectiveness in security alert analysis across key evaluation criteria.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides background on Large Language Models and their relevance to cybersecurity. Section 3 presents a survey of LLM-based approaches in security testing. Section 4 focuses on how LLMs are employed for network monitoring and threat detection. Section 5 presents a concrete use case of LLM-based security alert analysis through a comparative evaluation of three open-access LLMs for analyzing alerts produced by popular security monitoring tools. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and discusses future work.

2 Background

The background of LLMs [20] in cybersecurity intertwines the evolution of language models with the growing importance of cyberdefense and the escalating threats of cyberattacks. LLMs, or Large Language Models, have progressively evolved from early pattern recognition chatbots like Eliza in the 1960s [10] to sophisticated transformer-based models like GPT-3 [16] and beyond.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) has been the backbone of LLM development, with significant milestones such as the introduction of long short-term memories (LSTMs) and the Stanford CoreNLP suite, which provided a suite of algorithms for intricate NLP tasks [23]. However, it was the advent of transformer architecture that truly revolutionized the field, paving the way for the development of highly effective LLMs.

Transformer-based models, exemplified by T5 [15] and GPT-3, marked a breakthrough in NLP and unleashed a wave of innovation in LLM development. These models applied language modeling techniques in pre-trained LLMs, enabling them to handle a wide range of tasks by altering spans with a single mask. The sheer size and complexity of models like GPT-3, with its 175 billion parameters, demonstrated the unprecedented capabilities of LLMs in understanding and generating human-like text.

As LLM technology advanced, specialized models tailored for specific domains emerged. Models like Xuan Yuan 2.0 [31], designed for financial chat applications, and HuaTuo [30], focusing on medical knowledge, showcased the versatility of LLMs in addressing industry-specific needs. Fine-tuning LLMs became increasingly common, allowing organizations to customize models to meet their unique requirements and improve business functions.

However, alongside their tremendous potential, LLMs also posed challenges in terms of deployment and security. The high costs associated with running and training LLMs, coupled with extensive hardware requirements, limited their widespread utilization. Moreover, concerns regarding the safety and ethical implications of LLMs prompted researchers to explore techniques such as parameter tuning, knowledge distillation, and retrieving support evidence from external knowledge bases to enhance the effectiveness and reliability of LLM deployment.

In the realm of cybersecurity, the application of LLMs holds immense promise for both defense and offense [19]. The exponential growth of scientific literature related to LLMs reflects their proven efficacy across various functions, including cybersecurity. While previous studies have explored the safety aspects of LLMs, the focus has shifted towards understanding their role in cyberdefense and cyberattack scenarios [8].

In conclusion, the evolution of LLMs has been intertwined with the advancements in NLP and the growing demands of various industries, including cybersecurity. As LLM technology continues to mature, its application in cybersecurity is poised to play a pivotal role in defending against evolving threats and mitigating the risks posed by cyberattacks.

3 LLMs for Security Testing

Security testing plays a pivotal role in safeguarding digital assets and infrastructure against cyber threats. It encompasses a range of methodologies aimed at identifying vulnerabilities, assessing risks, and ensuring the robustness of systems and applications in the face of evolving security challenges. Traditional security testing methods often struggle to keep pace with the dynamic threat landscape and the increasing complexity of modern software and systems. Manual testing processes can be time-consuming, resource-intensive, and prone to human error. Moreover, the rapid deployment of new technologies and the proliferation of interconnected devices exacerbate the challenges of identifying and mitigating security vulnerabilities effectively.

3.1 LLM Capabilities in Security Contexts

LLMs are transforming security testing by automating complex tasks such as code analysis, log inspection, and vulnerability detection. Their ability to understand and generate natural language, code, and structured data makes them well-suited for identifying weaknesses across diverse system components. LLMs also enable adaptive security testing frameworks that can evolve in response to emerging threats. Furthermore, LLMs offer significant potential in augmenting both offensive and defensive cybersecurity operations by providing intelligent reasoning and automation capabilities across a wide range of testing scenarios.

More specifically, LLMs contribute to security testing in several key ways. They can automate code and configuration analysis by interpreting source code,

scripts, and configuration files to identify common security flaws such as hard-coded secrets, insecure function usage, and policy misconfigurations. Their natural language understanding and generation capabilities enable them to process unstructured text—including logs, alerts, and documentation—for tasks such as threat detection, vulnerability reporting, and incident summarization. For instance, studies such as [26] have applied LLMs to web content filtering, improving URL classification accuracy. LLMs also support reasoning and decision-making by assisting analysts in interpreting attack scenarios, generating threat models, and recommending remediation steps based on contextual information. As an example, [29] demonstrated the use of LLMs in generating honeywords to deceive attackers. Additionally, LLMs can create synthetic payloads, test cases, and malicious inputs through prompt-based fuzzing [18], helping to uncover vulnerabilities in applications, APIs, or protocols. Finally, pretrained on extensive technical corpora, LLMs serve as knowledge-rich assistants, capable of integrating and enriching information throughout both manual and automated security testing workflows.

In security contexts, these capabilities enable LLMs to act as versatile tools for both offensive and defensive tasks. They can assist penetration testers in crafting exploits or suggest improvements to security controls during audits. Moreover, their capacity to interpret heterogeneous data formats (e.g., logs, source code, CVEs, threat intel reports) makes them highly valuable in environments that require cross-domain reasoning. However, it is important to note that while LLMs excel at pattern recognition and language generation, they are not inherently trustworthy or deterministic. Their outputs can vary depending on prompts, and they may occasionally hallucinate or suggest insecure

3.2 LLM-based Tools for Security Testing

In recent years, there has been a proliferation of tools harnessing the power of LLMs for security and penetration testing. These tools leverage advanced natural language processing and deep learning techniques to automate various aspects of the security testing workflow, including vulnerability identification, threat detection, and report generation. Several notable LLM-based tools used for security testing are listed below:

- PENTESTGPT [11]: PENTESTGPT is an automated penetration testing system driven by LLMs. Developed by Deng et al., this tool facilitates complex tasks such as question answering, summarization, and reasoning in penetration testing scenarios. PENTESTGPT comprises three self-interacting modules - reasoning, generation, and parsing - which collaborate to tackle penetration testing challenges effectively.
- VulDetect [22]: VulDetect is a transformer-based vulnerability detection framework that utilizes GPT-2, a Large Language Model, to detect anomalies in system logs. Fine-tuned on datasets containing vulnerable and non-vulnerable code, VulDetect demonstrates high efficiency in real-time vulnerability detection, making it a valuable asset in security testing arsenals.

- CyBERT [7]: CyBERT unveils a classifier for detecting cybersecurity feature claims, employing fine-tuning techniques on pre-trained BERT language models. Developed specifically for industrial control systems (ICS) device documentation, CyBERT aggregates reports to identify conflicting feature claims and enhance security testing in critical infrastructure environments.
- SecurityLLM [13]: Developed by Ferrag et al., SecurityLLM is a system designed for precise threat detection and data privacy. This framework utilizes Fixed-Length Language Encoding (FLLE) and Byte-level Byte-Pair Encoder (BBPE) Tokenizer to process text traffic data, enabling accurate identification of various cyber threats in IoT environments.
- SecureFalcon [12]: SecureFalcon is an LLM-based cybersecurity reasoning system focused on detecting software flaws. Fine-tuned with a dataset of C code instances, SecureFalcon employs binary classification techniques to distinguish between vulnerable and non-vulnerable patterns, thereby enhancing security testing outcomes.
- CySecBERT [9]: A variant of CyBERT, CySecBERT is a word embedding model based on BERT architecture. Developed by Bayer et al., CySecBERT is trained on diverse cybersecurity tasks, including malware detection, alert aggregation, and phishing website detection, showcasing its versatility in security testing applications.
- Generative-AI for Red Team Scenarios [14]: Garvey et al. explore the viability of using Generative-AI, including LLMs, to improve the development of Red Team scenarios in organizations. By constructing narratives based on input prompts, LLMs facilitate the creation of plausible and complex attack scenarios, enhancing creativity and imagination in security testing exercises.

These tools exemplify the diverse applications of LLMs in security testing, ranging from vulnerability detection and threat identification to scenario development and reasoning in penetration testing scenarios. Incorporating these tools into security testing workflows can significantly enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of cybersecurity assessments, empowering organizations to better defend against emerging threats and vulnerabilities.

4 LLMs for Monitoring and Detection

Effective monitoring and detection are critical components of cybersecurity strategies, enabling organizations to identify and respond to security incidents in real time. In today’s dynamic threat landscape, rapid adaptation to evolving threats is essential, highlighting the need for intelligent and automated monitoring solutions. Traditional approaches, such as rule-based or signature-based detection, often struggle to keep pace with sophisticated and fast-moving cyber threats. Key challenges include the inability to detect zero-day attacks, high false positive rates, limited scalability, and the difficulty of analyzing large volumes of data in real time. Moreover, legacy systems frequently lack the agility to counter the constantly evolving tactics of cyber adversaries. LLMs, powered by advanced

natural language processing, offer promising new capabilities to enhance monitoring and detection in cybersecurity.

4.1 LLMs for Real-time Monitoring and Anomaly Detection

Large Language Models (LLMs) offer advanced natural language understanding capabilities that can significantly enhance real-time monitoring and anomaly detection in cybersecurity. By processing and correlating vast volumes of structured and unstructured data, such as network logs, system events, and threat intelligence feeds, LLMs can identify anomalous patterns and extract actionable insights with greater accuracy and contextual relevance. Unlike traditional rule-based or statistical anomaly detection systems, LLMs excel at interpreting semantics and intent, enabling the identification of subtle deviations from baseline behavior that may signal emerging threats [28]. Their adaptability and capacity for unsupervised learning make LLMs well-suited for environments where threats evolve rapidly and labeled data is scarce.

4.2 Enhancing Threat Intelligence with LLM-powered Monitoring

LLMs have the potential to transform threat intelligence by enabling real-time extraction and synthesis of information from diverse textual sources. By analyzing data from open-source intelligence (OSINT), dark web forums, incident reports, and threat advisories, LLMs can uncover emerging attack trends, threat actor tactics, and indicators of compromise (IOCs) [17]. These models can automate the generation of intelligence summaries and enrich threat databases, thereby improving situational awareness and supporting more proactive threat mitigation. Furthermore, their multilingual and cross-domain capabilities allow for broader coverage of global threat landscapes, enhancing both strategic and operational cybersecurity efforts.

4.3 Tools Implementing LLMs for Monitoring and Detection

In recent years, there has been a proliferation of tools harnessing the power of Large Language Models (LLMs) for monitoring and detection in cybersecurity. These tools leverage advanced natural language processing capabilities and deep learning algorithms to automate various aspects of monitoring and detection workflows, from anomaly detection to threat intelligence analysis. Below is a curated list of notable tools implementing LLMs for monitoring and detection:

- CyBERT [7] and CySecBERT [9]: These tools are generic enough to be also used for monitoring and detection. They unveil a classifier for detecting cybersecurity anomalies on pre-trained BERT language models.
- HuntGPT [6]: HuntGPT is an innovative framework designed for cyber threat hunting and intelligence gathering, leveraging the power of natural language processing to sift through vast amounts of textual data for potential security risks. Its application extends to anomaly detection, identifying patterns indicative of cyber attacks, and proactive defense strategies.

- KARTAL [24]: KARTAL is a fine-tuned Language Model developed for detecting vulnerabilities in web applications. Employing a detector component controlled by prompts generated from a fuzzer component, KARTAL dynamically adapts to various scenarios, making it effective in identifying broken access control rules and other logical vulnerabilities.
- VisionGPT [27]: VisionGPT is a monitoring and detection platform that leverages LLMs to analyze security logs, identify suspicious patterns, and generate actionable alerts for Safe Visual Navigation

While LLMs offer significant potential for improving monitoring and detection capabilities in cybersecurity, their implementation poses several challenges and considerations. These include the need for robust training data, model interpretability, scalability, and the risk of adversarial attacks targeting LLM-based detection systems. Additionally, organizations must carefully evaluate the privacy and ethical implications of deploying LLMs for monitoring and detection purposes, ensuring compliance with regulatory requirements and ethical guidelines. By addressing these challenges and considerations, organizations can harness the full potential of LLMs to enhance their cybersecurity posture and effectively defend against evolving threats.

5 Use Case: LLM-Based Security Alert Analysis

Security monitoring systems generate numerous alerts that require expert analysis to determine severity, impact, and appropriate responses. Traditional rule-based systems often produce high false positive rates and lack contextual understanding. We demonstrate how LLMs can enhance security alert analysis through a comparative evaluation of three state-of-the-art open-access models: Mistral-7B, Qwen3-8B, and Llama3.1-8B.

5.1 Evaluation Framework and Methodology

We developed a security agent that leverages LLMs to analyze and evaluate security alerts from multiple sources. The system processes alerts from three widely used security monitoring tools: (i) Montimage Monitoring Tool (MMT) [2], a flexible network monitoring framework that captures and analyzes traffic in real-time using protocol-specific models; (ii) Snort [3], a signature-based intrusion detection and prevention system (IDS/IPS) known for its efficiency in detecting known threats; and (iii) Suricata [4], an advanced IDS/IPS and network security monitoring engine that supports multi-threading and deep packet inspection for high-performance traffic analysis.

The evaluation framework consists of three main components: Alert Ingestion, LLM-based Analysis and Quality Evaluation. The Alert Ingestion module is responsible for collecting and normalizing alerts from various security tools, ensuring consistent input for downstream processing. The LLM-based Analysis component processes these alerts using multiple large language models to

Fig. 1: Distribution of overall scores for each model.

generate comprehensive analyses, including explanations, severity assessments, impact evaluations, confidence scores, false positive likelihoods, mitigation recommendations, and relevant references. Finally, the Quality Evaluation module assesses the quality of the LLM-generated analyses based on five key criteria: accuracy, clarity, actionability, completeness, and false positive assessment.

To summarize, we evaluated three LLMs using a dataset of 144 security alerts, comprising 24 MMT, 45 Snort, 45 Suricata, and 30 Suricata-CSV alerts.

5.2 Evaluation Results and Analysis

Results. Our comparative analysis revealed significant differences in how each LLM performed in security alert analysis, as shown in Figure 1. Qwen3-8B demonstrated the strongest overall performance (average score: 4.08/5), particularly excelling in completeness (4.50/5) and clarity (4.46/5). Llama3.1-8B showed balanced performance (average score: 3.85/5) with exceptional clarity (4.65/5), while Mistral-7B had the lowest overall score (3.72/5) but still provided valuable analysis. Figure 2 illustrates the analysis of model performance by alert type. Snort alerts were generally handled most effectively across all models (average score: 4.00/5), while Suricata alerts presented the greatest challenge (average score: 3.70/5). Notably, Qwen3-8B showed exceptional performance with MMT alerts (4.33/5), demonstrating its ability to interpret complex network traffic patterns. Figure 3 displays the breakdown of performance by evaluation criterion. All models achieved their highest scores in clarity (average: 4.50/5), underscoring the ability of LLMs to convey complex security concepts in a clear and understandable manner. False positive assessment was consistently the weakest

Fig. 2: Comparison of model performance across different alert types.

area (2.88/5), highlighting the challenge of determining alert legitimacy without additional context.

Analysis. Our evaluation yielded several important insights. First, in terms of contextual understanding, LLMs outperform traditional rule-based systems by interpreting security alerts within broader threat landscapes. They can connect alerts to known attack patterns and offer richer, more informative analyses. For instance, when analyzing an SSH brute force attack, Qwen3-8B achieved a high score of 4.75/5 by identifying specific IP addresses involved, suggesting concrete mitigation steps (including command-line examples), and referencing relevant CVEs and MITRE ATT&CK techniques. Second, model selection plays a critical role, as different LLMs exhibit varying strengths across alert types. The performance gap observed in MMT alert analysis (Qwen3-8B scoring 4.33/5 compared to Mistral-7B’s 3.52/5) suggests that security operations centers may benefit from a multi-model strategy tailored to specific alert sources. Third, while all models demonstrated strengths in clarity and explanation, they struggled with false positive assessment, highlighting the need for additional environmental context to enhance detection accuracy. Finally, LLMs showed promise in generating actionable intelligence, often including specific, implementable mitigation steps that can accelerate incident response and enhance security posture. Notably, a positive correlation between accuracy and completeness (correlation coefficient: 0.68) suggests that more thorough analyses tend to be more accurate as well.

Future Directions. While our results demonstrate the significant potential of LLMs in enhancing security alert analysis, several challenges remain. Future

Fig. 3: Comparison of model performance across different evaluation criteria.

work should focus on implementing feedback mechanisms that enable security analysts to improve future analyses, enhancing models with organization-specific context to better assess false positives, developing ensemble approaches that leverage the strengths of different models based on alert type, and optimizing inference speed to ensure effective deployment in time-sensitive security operations environments.

This use case demonstrates that LLMs can serve as valuable assistants to security analysts, helping to reduce alert fatigue, improve response times, and enhance the overall effectiveness of security operations. The comparative analysis highlights the importance of model selection and evaluation frameworks in security applications, paving the way for more intelligent and contextually aware security monitoring systems.

6 Conclusion & Future Work

In this paper, we explore the applications of LLMs in cybersecurity testing and monitoring, focusing on their role, challenges, and opportunities. We present a survey of LLMs, discuss their use in security testing, particularly for network monitoring and detection, and demonstrate how LLMs can enhance security alert analysis through a comparative evaluation of three open-access models: Mistral-7B, Qwen3-8B, and Llama3.1-8B. Overall, LLMs have significant potential in automating security processes, helping organizations identify vulnerabilities and detect threats more effectively.

Further research and development are needed to address challenges associated with LLM integration, including bias mitigation, interpretability, and security considerations. Additionally, we plan to extend LLMs for different security purposes, such as integrating them into the MMT-DPI plugin [1] to automatically extract attributes from new protocols or employing LLMs for managing contradictions in predefined playbooks for Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response (SOAR) platforms [21].

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